

An Invasion of AI in Retail Sector - “Staffless and Storeless”

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Kumar, A. Senthil, and R. Seranmadevi. “An Invasion of AI in Retail Sector - ‘Staffless and Storeless.’” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 208–14.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1403617>

Dr.A.Senthil Kumar

*Assistant Professor, School of Commerce Studies
Jain Deemed-to-be-University, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India*

Dr.R.Seranmadevi

*Associate Professor, School of Commerce Studies
Jain Deemed-to-be-University, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India*

Abstract

Retailing industry in India and all over the globe are experiencing the vibrant changes with respect to advent of technology. Artificial Intelligence (AI) also the one new emergent technology invaded in to the Retail industry to provide upend and most luxurious experience in shopping world to every shoppers. This AI technology enhances the retail world both in online as well as in offline. In helps the retailers to provide a new shopping experience to the customers by providing huge sum of valuable information at one point. The shoppers also have a chance to enjoy the technological advent with personalized excitement. It is expected that 50 percent of the retail companies will adapt to cloud-based services in the coming years that will look after their Big Data and analytics, ensuring a smooth process, reduce costs and increase flexibility. Staffless and Stockless are the natural evolution for retail outlets. Through Artificial Intelligence, businesses of all types and size will save thousands per month. This conceptual research paper analyses the need for changes in the retail industry in AI era. It narrates the way to extend these changes benefit the retailers to do their businesses effectively and efficiently and the consumers to get retail experience and gained out of it. Finally a model was constructed to depict the retail industry transformation through AI technology to engrave the benefits of retailer and shoppers as a whole.

Keywords: AI, automation, retailer, staffless, storeless

Introduction

The retail industry is always has a thrust to engrave in its way of selling be completely aligned with the advent of technology. The retail world is considered to be the biggest platform where many number of aspirant and potential customers are frequently visited to fulfill their personal requirements through shopping. It is mandatory for the retailers to provide valuable information in an adequate manner at timely way that too in a personalized manner to attract and retain the loyal customers under the hectic competitive and big data arena. Now-a-days the shoppers like to prefer the retail store at their own ease and assuring pleasure in shopping through personalized way under technological advancement. They like to experience the shopping at most comfortable way like living room experience. They

are not ready to spend their valuable time just for searching the articles and physically engaging themselves in to shopping. All these expectations are fulfilled and the customized services can be offered by the retailers can be possible only with the most advanced technology like Artificial Intelligence.

According to the report of Infosys (2017), Retail sector has invested more amounts for supply chains to become more web-centric and the variety of technologies including Artificial Intelligence (AI), robotics, logistics automation, data analytics and self-service technologies in an effort to become more competitive, more customer-centric and more responsive demand and opportunity. Amrita Nair-Ghaswalla (2018), retail giants such as Amazon, Walmart and Starbucks and other brands are rapidly transforming the retail industry through technology advancements, and these are turning to augmented reality, facial recognition and virtual apps to boost their marketing. AI facilitates the businesses and consumers will get benefitted from reduced costs, improved efficiency and more choices. This is the age of ‘always on’ consumers, who is changing faster than ever. Consumers expect connected and seamless experiences that make their lives easier. Emerging technologies in retail sector facilitate to deliver richer in-store experiences. Staffless and Stockless are the natural evolution for retail outlets.

Research Problem

In Indian Retail industry, the adoption of AI technology is not yet completely being happened. Till today, the invasion of AI in Indian retail sector is viewed as emerging technology. With the solicited features and comprehensive technological advancement will help the retailers to customize their offers to cater the needs of individual shoppers in India. By observing the tendency of retailing industry in a highly literally populated country like India, it can be easily judged even by a layman, the invasion of AI in Indian Retail sector cannot be postponed, this event will happen very shortly. In a globalized economy, India evidenced with the high young literate population having thrust to adopt any new technology in a massive successful way, so AI also inevitable from this history. Currently retailers are cater into the digital retail scene could fundamentally alter the way people engage with retail products and service, finally there is a million dollar question in the minds of retailers is that ‘Will it helps to reshape the cost dynamics of retail stores?’.

Research Objectives

The main objectives of this research are

- 1) To analyse the recent technological changes in the retail industry.
- 2) To study the invasion of AI technology in Retail industry.
- 3) To evaluate the staffless and storeless concept in Retail Industry.
- 4) To develop the conceptual model for retail transformation through AI technology.

Research Question

There are many reasons for the retailers to cope with the technological changes. In U.S, over 6,700 retail stores have been closed in 2017 because of emergence of e-commerce and rising labour cost. Around 29 states in the U.S have adopted minimum wage system higher than the federal minimum wages. In the retail sector, shrinkage due to shoplifting, employee theft, paperwork errors and supplier fraud are hard to fight. On the other side, consumers are demanding better, more innovative ways to shop and stores cannot keep up. Recent survey of Adyen & 451 Research (May 1, 2018) revealed that U.S retailers lost \$37.7 billion last year due to shoppers not wanting to wait in line, 80 per cent of shoppers have walked out of a store because of a line and 75 per cent of shoppers would shop more in-store with a “just walk out” payment experience. It was realized that

the major cost constructive fields in retail industry are Staff, restocking, and real estate. How could the gaps be bridged with the advent of AI technology to serve the customer better?

Theoretical Framework: Emergence of AI in Retail Sector

Artificial Intelligence is a smarter concept of machines being able to carry out human tasks that is considered intelligent while Stanford University defines Machine Learning (ML) as the science of getting computers to act without being explicitly programmed. AI and ML are often used interchangeably. However, they are different concepts used very frequently around subjects such as Cloud computing and Big Data Analytics. Among all sectors, the wide-ranging use of AI in retail sector is creating most buzz. Streamlining the retail processes and allowing online experiences to resemble human interactions is helping the digital retail to make a rapid progress. AI is now capable of analyzing, respond to and even predict customers’ questions and even behaviours, with a great potential for streamlining the way consumers discover and interact with products. Adoption of AI tools will certainly lead to increased accuracy and timeliness over conventional retail systems. Several companies are using AI, it can be safely assumed that while AI is a new technology being used by a lot of start-ups, how they use it and what they ultimately deliver is the key.

As recent independent research conducted by Infosys (2017) in global retail sector found that retailers have been using AI systems as part of their operations for an average of two years, with 44 per cent using AI technology in between one and three years, with a further 20 per cent actively using AI for over five years. Overall, 87 per cent of retailers surveyed have deployed some form of AI or automation technology as part of their operations and decision-making processes not just or data analytics, but to actually automate decision-making and guidance for human decision makers.

Staffless and Storeless– A Retail 2.0 Experience

Staffless is a form of organizational structure where the system allows unmanned or semi-manned retail stores. The staffless retail store is an automated retail system that allows convenience store operators to remove all or most of the labours while significantly reducing theft. Unmanned store allows the customer DIY (Do it Yourself) shopping. A mobile phone with new app can be used to take care of scanning and paying for items in staffless retailing. The staffless system eliminates labors (except stocking) and allows the customers to enter the store through a retailer’s mobile app loaded with their ID and Credit Card information which connects to a Smart Lock. Someone can only enter the store if they are provided with legitimate ID. The retailers can realize who are the customers are entered in to the store and available inside therein. With the stores experience, customers can just scan anything they wish to buy with their mobile device, place the items in their bag and walk out; there is no longer a need for a human to ring them up. When there are in staffless store, they are monitored by cameras that have surrounded with Artificial Intelligence back end. If a customer unknowingly places the unscanned articles in his basket, the AI technology alerts the shoppers and automatically add the bills to the shopper’s card. If the same was intentionally happened, then the particular shoppers will be blocked to do further transactions in the retail shops.

Staffless system has been working in Europe for over a year in a number of different stores. The Moby Mart - a Sweden based retail sector has initiated this staffless process, where the registered customers swipe a QR code on their device for their shopping activity. Shoppers scan groceries and other items into the app for making purchases, and as they leave, the store automatically charges their credit card. Currently there is no sales representative on staff, engineers at Moby Mart. It is functioning with artificial intelligence powered holographic shop assistant to help with purchases. Chinese retailers, such as Alibaba, have already initiated smart stores that use machine learning, biometric recognition, and sensors to track customers, their purchases through mobile payment

systems, such as Alipay and WeChat Pay. China is in a way ahead in presenting this autonomous shopping experience and several more smart stores are expected to start in China over the next couple of years (Pragati Verma, 2017). BingoBox, a 24-hour cashier-free convenience store that just raised \$14 million plans to set up 5,000 smart stores within the year 2018.

Stockless

The most significant exercise for physical retailers is restocking and managing inventory. Unmanned stores offer more cost-effective and efficient ways to restock. Instead of human employees, retailer use sensors and data analytics software to track inventory. When stock runs low, the self-driving vehicle can simply return to the warehouse to replace the entire shelving unit with a full one. Cromwell (2017) uses this model which is much cheaper to run especially in prime real estate locations. “With a one-time investment in a mobile store, you don’t need to worry about growing rents denting your margins,” he added. Recently, retailers are restructuring their operations to embrace automation using robot. The robot maneuvers freely around the store, looking for out-of-stock items. It then reports data to the store’s backend operations to replenish missing items. Real time information are provided to robot to make easier for people to do their jobs and keep shelves full for customers. The ability to collect real-time information about products and customers using Internet of Things (IoT) and data analytics, could open new opportunities for retail stores that must compete with the growth in online shopping.

“Technology can change the game for offline stores. Smart, physical stores will be able to minimize friction in buying and create a personalized experience which, until now was only available online” (Cromwell 2017). Big data analysis are considered as the major technology support the retailers to observe the present behaviour of the customers, gather the shopper’s history at every transactions, stored that information and used the same to predict the future sales level of the retailers. Sometimes, with the huge volume of data, the retailers can even able to predict the futuristic demand for them through data mining technology. It will also help them to capture the shoppers through customized deals and offer valid suggestions for their requirements. Some retail world use the AI technology to give the shopping experience only with their mobile phone by providing the scanner facility for every object they deal with, through the authenticated app developed and delivered by the concerned retailers the shoppers simply scan the material they like to buy will automatically added in to their respective shopping baskets and the money also be debited from their concerned bank account through debit/credit cards. The other retailers attempt to provide OMNI channel retailing through merging too many retailing strategy under single basket.

A Sweden based Moby Mart is the first autonomous staffless mobile store (2017) turning every parking space in the world into a potential new 24-hour store, automatically prepares to restock when running out of important items. There is no need for moving goods from trucks, instead the entire store will run back to the warehouse to restock or even dock with other Moby Marts to refill. The cloud knows where they are, it can help them find a place to meet and exchange products. Stockless store can be operated either manually or controlled by remote as well. The shopping experience is programmed by a virtual assistant who receives each customer.

VNTANA and Satisfi Labs in Los Angeles (September 2017), Leading Augmented Reality hologram company have announced a new platform that will allow businesses to develop a hologram concierge to be used in business (Tom Ward, 2017). The company has launched the first-ever artificial intelligence hologram concierge for retail, sports and hospitality. The project fuses artificial intelligence (AI) with augmented reality (AR) technology to produce a 3D persona that can interact with customers. The industry-first experience allows the hologram to react and respond to consumers’ questions without the need for wearables or a touch screen device while

collecting data on the consumer. The hologram concierge is powered by VNTANA’s patented hardware and software that projects an interactive 3D persona who answers questions based on Satisfi Labs’ custom AI said by Ashley Crowder, VNTANA’s CEO and co-founder. In this cloud based technology, all the information are stored in cloud, which will benefit to identify the diverse tastes of consumers and big data analysis on general customer behaviour with knowledge about the tastes of individual customers, helps to predict what products will sell at what places. Stockless system provides safe and reliable environment for the retail system. A rapid and complete store audit is being done by robot, virtual assistants. At present, the Google and Amazon are spending huge amount on making virtual assistants as smart as a human being. They are making money through advertising and its all about data they have about customers. They are gathering rich datasets to inform stocking decisions. Stockless retail provides store featuring no assistance from store personnel and self-checkouts within five minutes.

Research Model

The following are the figures displaying benefits of staff less proposition and storeless proposition and the final conceptual model depicting the transformation of retail industry through AI technology and the ultimate benefits reaped by the retailers and shoppers as a whole.

Figure: 1 Benefits of Staffless Proposition*

Figure: 2 Benefits of Stockless Proposition*

Model for Retail transformation through AI

Figure: 3 Retail transformation through AI*

*Developed by Researchers

Conclusion

With some jobs potentially evolving into new roles where people will oversee, manage and augment AI and automation systems, employees may also be worried about being unfairly judged on their AI and automation skills and education rather than their career experience. Careful consideration must be given to the impact an AI deployment will have on a business to ensure that employees and customers come along for the ride. This study can be extended for further quantitative research by getting opinion from the shoppers and retailers. This study may be used to students, sellers, manufacturers, research companies and advertising agencies show special interest in analyzing recent developments in retail industry during this AI era.

References

- Adyen. 451 Research (2018). New study: Long lines cost US retailers \$37.7 billion, <https://www.adyen.com/blog/new-study-long-lines-cost-us-retailers-377-billion>
- Amrita Nair, Ghaswalla. (2018). Rewiring the shopping experience, Business Line, P.2
- Ari Rosenblum (January 22, 2018), Staffless.AI, <https://app.slidebean.com/p/2jykKb4NkS/store-owners-stafflessai-pd-v2#1>
- Brand Wagen. Financial Express (June 5, 2018), Consumer's Leisure Behaviour, pp.3
- First-Ever Responsive AI Hologram Launched By VNTANA and Satisfi Labs Partnership <http://www.businessinsider.com/swedens-unmanned-convenience-store-2016-2>
- <http://www.tffa.com/blog/tffa-daily-buzz-3511/post/attn-retailers-staffless-ai-seeks-store-for-beta-test-in-austin-first-in-u-s-8997>
- <https://futurism.com/a-new-artificially-intelligent-hologram-was-just-born/>
- <https://uk.reuters.com/>
- <https://www.delltechnologies.com/en-us/perspectives/this-staffless-grocery-store-may-be-self-driving-to-a-neighborhood-near-you/>
- <https://www.digitaltrends.com/cool-tech/sweden-app-enabled-automated-store/>
- <https://www.forbes.com>
- <https://www.onartificialintelligence.com/articles/11418/worlds-first-autonomous-staffless-mobile-store>
- <https://www.statista.com/statistics/183499/the-most-popular-retailers-on-facebook/>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iB0ljPrCZ3g>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ShNL3oU4Mi0>
- Infosys Limited (2017), External Document-AI: The Promise of a great future for retailers, Source: Amplifying human potential – towards purposeful artificial intelligence, pp.4.
- Pragati Verma. (2017). This Staffless Grocery Store May Be Self-Driving To A Neighborhood Near You, Dell Perspectives Contributor, <https://www.forbes.com/>

sites/ delltechnologies/2017/12/06/this-staffless-grocery-store-may-be-self-driving-to-a-neighborhood-near-you/#2ee1b1492263

Staffless AI Seeks Store for Beta Test in Austin, First in U.S.

Technology Trends (2017), Artificial Intelligence – Paving way in Indian Retail Industry, <https://www.fieldassist.in/blog/artificial-intelligence-indian-retail-industry/>

Tom Ward. (2017). Avatar Sequels Could Be Shown in 3D That Doesn't Require Glasses, <https://futurism.com/avatar-sequels-could-be-shown-in-3d-that-doesnt-require-glasses/>

VNTANA, Los Angeles, September 26, 2017, <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/first-ever-responsive-ai-hologram-launched-by-vntana-and-satisfi-labs-partnership-300525882.html>

Wan-I., Lee., Shan-Yin Cheng., & Yu-Ta Shih, (2017). Effects among product attributes, involvement, word-of-mouth, and purchase intention in online shopping, *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 22, 223-229. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2017.07.007>